

AL-FIR FORTRESS: ARXEOLOGICAL STUDY OF THE MIDDLE CENTURY QIAT (KAT) FORTRESS

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University Keywords: Qiyat (Kat), Al-Fir Fortress, medieval Khorezm, archaeological excavation, Afrighid dynasty, Abu Rayhan Biruni, stratigraphy, cultural layer, ceramics, numismatics, Khorezm Archaeological Expedition, citadel (shahristan, ark, rabad), historical topography.

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Abstract: This article systematically analyzes the history of archaeological research on Qiyat (Kat), one of the ancient capitals of medieval Khorezm. It examines field research conducted by the Khorezm Archaeological and Ethnographic Expedition since the mid-20th century, covering the stratigraphy of the city's cultural layers and the architectural features of the Al-Fir fortress complex. Drawing on medieval written sources — including Abu Rayhan Biruni, Yaqut, and Ibn Battuta — as well as modern scholarly work, the study scientifically substantiates the city's developmental stages from the 6th–7th centuries BC through the 15th–17th centuries, the construction techniques using raw brick and clay, and the periodization of the city based on numismatic evidence. The findings serve as a significant source for understanding the material culture and development dynamics of medieval Khorezm cities.

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